

PROTECTING THE ENVIRONMENT FOR STUDENTS FORMATION OF CONCEPTS

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Abstract: *To ensure the protection of the environment and rational use of nature. Nature protection today requires public attention. In our country, effective use of land, underground resources, plants, and animal world, their protection on a scientific basis, the purity of water and air. Concepts about conservation and environmental protection are given.*

Key words: *environmental planning, standardization, expertise, licensing, certification.*

Introduction Environmental protection and use of nature.

In our country, effective use of land, underground resources, plants, and animal world, their protection on a scientific basis, preservation of water and air purity, and environmental protection are carried out on the basis of the requirements stated in the Constitution. A large number of regulatory documents on the use, protection and restoration of natural resources have been adopted. Laws

and decisions consider land, forest, and underground resources as state property, and their protection is indicated. In recent years, effective work has been carried out in our republic in terms of environmental protection and economical use of natural resources. Zero, the acceptability of the ecological policy implemented in our republic depends to a large extent on the extent to which ecology, in particular, ecological problems are solved. A brief analysis of the influence of man

and society on nature shows that the main factor that destroys nature is that people treat nature in a wrong, irrational, unruly manner in the process of meeting their needs. The main way to prevent negative human impact on nature is to correctly understand the laws of nature and society. And their rational use for human benefit. It is important for a person to properly master nature and maintain the relationship between nature and society at the optimal level. For this, it is necessary that a certain system of ecological knowledge is sufficiently formed in a person. Therefore, it is one of the most urgent issues of the present time that every member of the society should have ecological knowledge, regardless of who he is and what his duties are. Compared to 2004, the number of instruments needed to measure environmental pollution increased by 11%. In 2008, 30 places were found to be more polluted than the standard. If there are enterprises that emit toxic substances into the atmosphere in excess of the norm, they will be immediately stopped by environmental officials. Violators who kill plants, animals and fish carefully grown in reserves and reservations will also be severely punished. At the moment, the areas where the large constructions, factories, and residential buildings will be built will be

subjected to ecological expertise. As a result of the ecological expertise, the soil composition of this place will be answered whether the building will not sink after heavy buildings fall, or whether there is no radioactive substance or residue here, whether it will harm people's health and other questions. Now, industry experts and standard workers are burning their souls about the environmental purity of food products brought from abroad. The first problem is the State Committee for Nature Conservation and Uzgidromet. according to the data of the station, the quality of drinking water is not very satisfactory. The water content of Amudarya, Syrdarya, Surkhandarya, Kashkadarya and Zarafshan rivers has not changed much, these rivers belong to the 3rd class according to water purity. The amount of hexavalent chromium and copper in the Karasuv canal water does not exceed the permitted standard. The level of nitrogen nitrate in the water has fallen below the permissible level. The above information indicates that certain works are being done in the Republic in terms of environmental protection and conservation and use of natural resources. A sharp increase in the number of industrial enterprises and machines in the republics. It also shows the need to pay more attention to industrial ecology. Industrial

ecology cannot be imagined without economic diversions and financial investments of nature users. In order to protect mother nature from the effects of anthropogenic and man-made factors, it is necessary to follow the working program developed by the State. Industrial ecology, if neglected in large cities, causes enormous damage to people living in nature and to the atmospheric air pool, soil and drinking water. Today, ecology has become a global problem beyond the scope of a certain region or republic, as we can see in the following problems.

A second major problem is acid rain, the human-induced release of ozone, carbon and sulfur dioxide, and other gases from the upper atmosphere back to the earth as precipitation. Wherever acid rain falls, it enriches the soil with toxic substances, destroys the activity of microorganisms in the soil, and the plant that sprouts from this soil takes some of these toxic products with it, thus passing to the human body, causes serious diseases. Also, after the animals eat these plants, the products of the plant become unfit for consumption, or they pass from non-ecologically clean products to the human body. There is always a certain amount of dust in the atmosphere. It is formed as a result of natural phenomena occurring in nature.

Such dust can be divided into 3 types: mineral (inorganic), organic and space dust. The erosion and weathering of rocks, the eruption of volcanoes, the burning of forests and forests, and the burning of seawater into salt in the air cause the formation of mineral dust. Organic dust is formed due to air-dwelling aeroplankton organisms, bacteria, spores, plant seeds, humus and waste of plants and animals. Space dust is the burnt remains of meteorites during their passage through the atmosphere.

The third problem is common in industrially developed cities, air pollution causes respiratory and skin diseases in people, where ozone, carbon dioxide and sulfur dioxide enter the atmosphere, human health deteriorates in such rainy weather. Cereal crops, vegetable crops become unfit for consumption, agriculture suffers a lot from such rains. It also rusts or corrodes all types of metals. The fourth problem is the "Pamikov effect" or "Pamik effect", the smoke of thick gases containing carbon dioxide rises up and surrounds the earth, preventing the passage of sunlight into open space, as a result of which the air on the earth warms and the climate changes. leads to change. According to further reports, it is estimated that in the near future (50-60 years) the Arctic and Antarctic

ices will melt and the volume of the waters of the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans will rise to a height of approximately 50 meters. Due to the rise of ocean waters, a number of coasts of Europe, Africa and Australia will be flooded. One of the means that pollutes nature in the largest amount is oil processing and waste of radioactive substances. Flora and fauna of plants die directly under the influence of pollution. In various parts of the globe, the soil where plants grow becomes unusable, desertification, salinization, the increase of waterless and arid regions, the decrease of forests that produce tons of oxygen, and the drying of natural wetlands also lead to the deterioration of their natural state. will come.

Conclusion Society's impact on nature can be direct and hidden.

Direct impact means the overt influence of people on nature. Mining of underground minerals, use of forests are consequences of direct impact on nature. For example, extraction of mineral resources leads not only to the violation of biogeocenoses in the area of active mines, mines, quarries, but also to the violation of the hydrogeological regime of neighboring natural areas. It accelerates the occurrence of local droughts in places, changes the world of animals and plants, and causes

disruption of processes related to the supply of water in the soil. Therefore, it is one of the most urgent issues of the present time that every member of the society should have ecological knowledge, regardless of who he is and what kind of task he performs.

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